

ULTRA STRONG, STIFF AND MULTIFUNCTIONAL CARBON NANOTUBE COMPOSITES

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It has been a challenge for two decades to assemble the extremely strong carbon nanotubes (CNTs) into macroscopic CNT composites that break the strength ceiling of carbon fiber composites. Here we report the fast incorporation of long CNTs into polymer matrix using a novel approach, stretch-winding, to produce composites that are much stronger than any current engineering composite (see Fig. 1). The CNT composites reach a strength of 3.8 GPa (see Fig. 2), an excellent electrical conductivity and a high thermal conductivity (see Fig. 3). These superior properties are primarily derived from the long length, high volume fraction, good alignment and reduced waviness of the CNTs that are produced. The combination of high strength and excellent

electrical and thermal conductivities makes CNT composites a promising enabler of new aerospace technologies and adventures.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic illustration of the concept of straightening CNTs before embedding them in polymer matrix in a layer-by-layer fashion. (b) Schematic illustration of the experimental setup for the stretch-winding process.

Figure 2. (a) Comparison of the tensile strength and Young's Modulus of currently available engineering carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites (CFRP) as well as CNT reported previously. Note that all data are from composite samples. The blue filled squares are from existing high-strength CFRP and the green filled diamonds are from those of currently existing high-modulus CFRP. The unfilled circles are best CNT composites reported previously [9, 22, 27]. (b) Comparison of the specific tensile strength and specific modulus of the stretch-wound composites with the best engineering CFRP. The data were calculated based on a density of 1.6 g cm^{-3} for CFRP (60 vol.%) and 1.4 g cm^{-3} for the stretch-wound composites (46 vol.%).

Figure 3. (a) Typical stress-strain curves of pristine CNT sheet, unstretched and stretched composites, demonstrating a significant improvement of the mechanical properties through aligning and straightening of CNTs. Effect of stretching on (b) tensile strength and (c) Young's modulus, (d) thermal conductivity, and (e) electrical conductivity of the composites.